

***L*-Premerotopic Spaces**

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Abstract

The present paper introduces *L*-premerotopic spaces and aims to study their lattice structure. We define a method to obtain an *L*-merotopic space from a given *L*-premerotopic space. Finally, it is obtained that the family of all *L*-premerotopies on a set *X* is a complete distributive lattice.

Key words: Merotopic spaces, *L*-premerotopic spaces, Nearness spaces

1. Introduction

In 1974, Herrlich [1] introduced the concept of nearness spaces by axiomatizing the concept of nearness of arbitrary collection of subset of *X*. It is a generalization of concept of two sets being near. Chattopadhyay and Njåstad [2] used the space satisfying four conditions of Herrlich's nearness space with name of merotopic space. Nearness spaces are those merotopic spaces for which a relationship exists between the near collection and the closure operator. Similar spaces are also studied by Ward [3] and Gagrat and Thron [4]. In fuzzy subset theory, nearness spaces were studied by Soetens and Wuyts in [5], using the concept of uniform covers. In 2008, Khare and Singh [6] introduced the concept of (*L*, *n*) –Merotopies which has restriction on the cardinality. We have shown in [7] that the category of binary *L*-merotopic space and *L*-merotopic maps is bireflective in the category of *L*-merotopic spaces and *L*-merotopic maps. In [8], we have presented a unified study of *L*-proximity, *L*-contiguity and *L* and *L*-merotopic maps.

Prerequisites for the present paper are collected in Section 2. In Section 3, the concept of *L*-premerotopic spaces is given. The family of all *L*-premerotopies on a set *X* forms a complete distributive lattice with respect to the order defined by set inclusion. Largest and smallest elements of this lattice are discrete and indiscrete *L*-spaces. As the intersection of *L*-premerotopies is an *L*-premerotopy, this method is used to obtain infimum of the family of given *L*-merotopies. Finally, it is obtained that the family of all *L*-premerotopies on a set *X* is a complete distributive lattice. We can obtain an *L*-merotopic space associated with it and so as an advantage we can have as many *L*-

merotopies on a space as there are Čech closure operators. Few more different examples are also given as an illustration. Where at one side the arbitrary union of L -merotopies and arbitrary intersection of F -premerotopies is an L -merotopy and an L -premerotopy (an L -merotopy with one condition dropped out) respectively, a question which remains open in this context is: 'arbitrary intersection of L -merotopies need not be an L -merotopy'. As a direct consequence of the statement, it is obtained that the family of all L -premerotopies forms a complete distributive lattice. Also, we constructed an L -merotopic space from a given L -premerotopic space and using it, the lattice structure on the family of all L -merotopic space is given.

2. Preliminaries

We first collect some preliminary notions and results. Let X be a non empty ordinary sets and L be a distributive and complete lattice with largest element $\mathbf{1}$, smallest element $\mathbf{0}$ and an order reversing involution from': $L \rightarrow L$. For $t \in L$, the element $f \in L^X$ defined by $f(x) = t$, for all $x \in X$ is denoted by t . An L -fuzzy subset in X is an element of the family L^X of all functions from X to L . An L -fuzzy point $x_p \in L^X$, $p \in L - \{0\}$ is defined by $x_p(x) = p$, $x_p(y) = 0$, $x \neq y$. Let $f \in L^X$, then support of f , denoted by $\text{supp } f$, is defined by $\text{supp } f = \{x \in X: f(x) > 0\}$.

Definition 2.1:-For A, B subsets of L^X , we say

- (i) A corefines B if for all $f \in A$, there exist $g \in B$ such that $f \geq g$,
- (ii) A refines B if for all $f \in A$, there exist $g \in B$ such that $f \leq g$
- (iii) $A \sim B$ if A corefines B and B corefines A ;
- (iv) $A \approx B$ if A refines B and B refines A

Definition 2.2 (Khare M, Singh R [6]):-Let X be a non empty set and $\xi \subseteq P(L^X)$. Then ξ is called an L -merotopy on X provided, for subsets A, B of L^X ,

- (i) A corefines B and $B \in \xi \Rightarrow A \in \xi$,
- (ii) $\bigwedge A \neq 0 \Rightarrow A \in \xi$,
- (iii) $\emptyset \neq \xi \neq P(L^X)$;
- (iv) $A \vee B \in \xi \Rightarrow A \in \xi \text{ or } B \in \xi$

The pair (X, ξ) is called an L -merotopic space.

3. L -Premerotopic Spaces

Definition 3.1. Let X be a nonempty set and $\xi \subseteq P(L^X)$. Then ξ is called an L -premerotopy on X provided, for the subsets A, B of L^X ,

- (M1) A corefines B and $B \in \xi \Rightarrow A \in \xi$,
- (M2) $\bigwedge A \neq 0 \Rightarrow A \in \xi$,
- (M3) $\emptyset \neq \xi \neq P(L^X)$.

The pair (X, ξ) an L -premerotopic space. An L -premerotopy ξ is called an L -merotopy if it satisfies an additional condition M4 [6].

Examples 3.2. Let X be a nonempty set. Then:

(i) $\xi = \{A \subseteq I^X : A \text{ corefines some } F\text{-filter } F \text{ on } X\}$. Then (X, ξ) is an F -premerotopic space. Observe that if $\bigwedge A \neq \mathbf{0}$, then there exists $x \in X$ such that $f(x) \neq 0$ for all $f \in A$. Hence A corefines the F -filter $\{f : f(x) \neq 0\}$.

Let $P_M(X) = \{\xi : \xi \text{ is an } L\text{-premerotopy on } X\}$. The family $P_M(X)$ is partially ordered by the relation ' \leq ' defined by $\xi_1 \leq \xi_2$ iff $\xi_1 \subseteq \xi_2$, for $\xi_1, \xi_2 \in P_M(X)$.

Theorem 3.3. Let $\{\xi_\alpha : \alpha \in I\}$, where I is an index set, be a nonempty subfamily of $P_M(X)$. Then

- (i) $\bigcup_\alpha \xi_\alpha$ is an L -premerotopy on X and $\bigvee \xi_\alpha = \sup \{\xi_\alpha : \alpha \in I\} = \bigcup_\alpha \xi_\alpha$;
- (ii) $\bigcap_\alpha \xi_\alpha$ is an F -premerotopy on X and $\bigwedge \xi_\alpha = \inf \{\xi_\alpha : \alpha \in I\} = \bigcap_\alpha \xi_\alpha$.

Proof. That $\bigcap_\alpha \xi_\alpha$ is an L -premerotopy on X can be seen as follows: if A corefines B and $B \in \xi_\alpha$ for all α , then $A \in \xi_\alpha$ for all α . If $\bigwedge A \neq \mathbf{0}$, then $A \in \xi_\alpha$ for all α and so $\bigcap_\alpha \xi_\alpha \neq \emptyset$. Also, if $\mathbf{0} \in A$, then $A \notin \xi_\alpha$ and $\{\mathbf{1}\} \in \xi_\alpha$, for all α .

Theorem 3.4. The family $P_M(X)$ is a complete distributive lattice. The largest and smallest elements of this lattice are discrete and indiscrete L -spaces respectively [6].

Proof. Follows from Theorem 3.3 and the fact that $\xi_1 \cup (\xi_2 \cap \xi_3) = (\xi_1 \cup \xi_2) \cap (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3)$ and $\xi_1 \cap (\xi_2 \cup \xi_3) = (\xi_1 \cap \xi_2) \cup (\xi_1 \cap \xi_3)$, $\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3 \in P_M(X)$.

Theorem 3.5. (i) Let (X, ξ) be an L -premerotopic space. Define $B \in \xi^*$ iff there do not exist finitely many elements A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n of $P(I^X) - \xi$ such that $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines B . Then (X, ξ^*) is an L -merotopic space.

(ii) Let $\{\xi_i : i \in I\}$ be a nonempty family of L -merotopies on a set X and $\xi = \bigcap_i \xi_i$. Then $\xi^* = \inf \{\xi_i : i \in I\}$.

Proof. The axiom (M1) follows from the definition. Let there exist finitely many elements A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n of $P(I^X) - \xi$ such that $C = A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines $B, B \in P(I^X)$. Then $\bigwedge A_i = \mathbf{0}$, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and so $\bigwedge (A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n) = (\bigwedge A_1) \vee (\bigwedge A_2) \vee \dots \vee (\bigwedge A_n) = \mathbf{0}$. Since C corefines B , there exists a subset B_1 of B such that C corefines B_1 . We have, $\mathbf{0} = \bigwedge_{f \in C} f \geq \bigwedge B_1 \geq \bigwedge B$. Hence

$\bigwedge B = \mathbf{0}$, i.e. (M2) is true. Also, $\xi^* \subseteq \xi$ and so $\xi^* \neq P(I^X)$. Axiom (M4) follows by

observing that if $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines B_1 and $C_1 \vee C_2 \vee \dots \vee C_m$ corefines B_2 , then $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee C_1 \vee C_2 \vee \dots \vee C_m$ corefines $B_1 \vee B_2$.

Propositon 3.5. If $\{\xi_\alpha : \alpha \in I\}$, where I is an index set is a family of L -merotopies on a set X , then $\cup \xi_\alpha$ is an L -merotopy on X .

Theorem 3.6. The family $M(X)$ of all L -merotopies on a set X is a complete distributive lattice with respect to the order defined by set inclusion.

Proof. Using 2.3.3 and Theorem 3.5, we obtain that $M(X)$ is a complete lattice. Now we show that, for $\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3 \in M(X)$, $\xi_1 \vee (\xi_2 \wedge \xi_3) = (\xi_1 \vee \xi_2) \wedge (\xi_1 \vee \xi_3)$; here $\vee \{\xi_i : i \in I\} = \cup \{\xi_i : i \in I\}$, $\xi_i \in M(X)$. Let $A \in \xi_1 \vee (\xi_2 \wedge \xi_3)$. Then either (i) $A \in \xi_1$ or (ii) $A \in \xi_2 \wedge \xi_3$. Let $A \in \xi_1$. For any finite number of A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n , if $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines A , then $A_i \in \xi_1$ for some i . Hence $A \in (\xi_1 \cup \xi_2) \wedge (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3)$. For case (ii), let there exist finitely many elements A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n of $P(I^X) - ((\xi_1 \cup \xi_2) \cap (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3))$ such that $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines A . Then either $A_i \notin (\xi_1 \cup \xi_2)$ or $A_i \notin (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3)$ for all i and in both cases $A_i \notin \xi_2 \cap \xi_3$ for all i . Hence $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n \in P(I^X) - (\xi_2 \cap \xi_3)$ such that $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines A , i.e. $A \notin (\xi_2 \wedge \xi_3)$.

Conversely, let $A \in (\xi_1 \cup \xi_2) \wedge (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3)$. Then there do not exist finitely many $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n \notin (\xi_1 \cup \xi_2) \cap (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3)$ such that $A_1 \vee A_2 \vee \dots \vee A_n$ corefines A . Then $A \in \xi_1 \cup (\xi_2 \wedge \xi_3)$ follows from the observation that $(\xi_1 \cup \xi_2) \cap (\xi_1 \cup \xi_3) \supseteq \xi_2 \cap \xi_3$.

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